

www.arseam.com

Impact Factor: 3.43

Cite this paper as : Alexander Olawumi Dabor & MeshackAggreh (2017), "ADOPTION OF INTERNATIONAL PUBLIC SECTOR ACCOUNTING BY GOVERNMENT MINISTRIES AND AGENCIES IN NIGERIA", *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management*, ISSN: 2348 –3954 (online) ISSN: 2349 –2546 (print), Volume 5,(Issue 5,May-2017), pp 52-65

ADOPTION OF INTERNATIONAL PUBLIC SECTOR ACCOUNTING BY GOVERNMENT MINISTRIES AND AGENCIES IN NIGERIA

Alexander Olawumi Dabor

Department of Accounting Veritas University, Abuja

MeshackAggreh

Department of Accounting Veritas University,
Abuja

ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to find out the prospects and challenges of adoptions of IPSAS by the Nigerian public sector. The study focused on federal ministries in Abuja. One hundred and fifty copies of questionnaire were distributed to civil servants in Abuja. The study employed Z-test statistical technique and chi-square. Data gathered from field was analyzed by MS-excel 2016. The result shows that adoption of IPSAS will increase the reliability of the reports prepared by Nigerian public sector. The result also shows that adoption of IPSAS will enhance better comparability of financial report among various state. Furthermore, the study shows that lack funds and internal resistance are major challenges facing the adoption of IPSAS. The study recommended that the federal government should release fund to power the switching over to IPSAS. Accountants in public should be trained on new accounting software that will enhance their understandability of IPSAS. Government should display the political toward adoption of IPSAS by mandating all ministries and government agencies to switch over to IPSAS and defaulters should be duly sanctioned.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Over the last thirty years the public sector has gone through a wave of reforms worldwide, usually towards the adoption of business-like practices in order to enhance improved utilization of public resources. These reforms have led changes in the mode of presentation of financial reports in the public sector. Adegbite (2010) argues that these changes become imperative because the modern day government day needs vital financial information in order perform business effectively. In recent times, countries of the world have set the standards of financial reporting in their individual territories. According to Earnest and Young (2012) globalization introduced into being an ever increasing collaboration, international trade and commerce among the countries of the world, hence there is need for increase in uniformity in reporting across the globe. The agitation for the introduction of a unified accounting standards has been the primary driver of International Public Sector Accounting Standards for public sector financial reporting. While the commercial entities across the world are moving toward international financial Reporting standards (IFRS), governments are harmonizing with International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS). The Public sector includes entities or organizations that implement public policy through the delivery of services and the redeployment of income and wealth, with both activities supported mainly by compulsory tax or levies on other sectors. This also comprises governments and all publicly owned, controlled and or publicly funded agencies, enterprises, and other entities of government that deliver public programs, goods, or services. Public sector accounting is a system or process which gathers, records, classifies and summarizes as reports the financial events existing in the public provide information to information users associated to public institutions.

Omolehinwa and Naiyeya (2003) opine that International Public Sector Accounting Standard (IPSAS) is the centerpiece of the "global revolution in government accounting in response to calls for and transparency. Apart

from accountability and transparency of IPSAS, is it a crucial prerequisite for accessing funds from World Bank. Developing countries are also admonished by international organizations which provide financial assistance to them to switch over to IPSAS. Other countries irrespective of their political and economic systems, are encouraged to switch over to IPSAS. () reports that IPSAS has become *de facto* international benchmarks for evaluating government accounting practices worldwide. For these reasons, IPSAS warrants the attention of accounting policy-makers, practitioners and academics alike. The conceptual issues are problem areas or debatable points on the substance of IPSAS. Institutional issues, on the other hand, relate to the governance and process of setting IPSAS.

() IPSASs supervise the recognition, measurement, presentation and disclosure requirements as it regards to transactions and events in general purpose financial statement. These kind financial reports are characterized by the fact that they are issued for users who are unable to demand financial information to enable them meet their specific information needs. Some scholars argue it is costly everywhere to produce and disseminate information, hence governments in all types of political systems lack the economic incentives to do so. () further document that political systems exert a greater demand for government accountability and transparency than others; for example, representative democracies are more demanding than authoritarian and totalitarian political systems. A democratic government is obliged to be more responsive to information demands placed upon it. This would be the case in developed countries and developing countries alike. However, the opportunity cost of resources used in improving government financial information is higher in developing countries than in developed countries. () opines governments in democratic developing countries may willing to undertake government accounting reform but restrained by the financial involvement. The author further argues that governments in non-democratic developing countries are both unenthusiastic and unable to afford cost of switching over to IPSAS. Local accounting standards in Nigeria were set under the Nigerian Accounting Standards Board Act of 2003 by the Nigerian Accounting Standards Board (NASB) now Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria. Nigeria is supposed to switch over to officially over to IPSAS 2014 but it is surprising that no government (federal, state or local) agency has really prepared it report using IPSAS. From foregoing the objective of this study is to ascertain the prospect and challenges of adoption of IPSAS in Nigeria

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Prospects of Adoption of IPSAS in Nigeria

In an attempt to join the on-going vehicle of global standard in the public Sector and to enjoy the benefits of the standard, the Federal Executive Council (FEC) in July 2010 approved the adoption of the International Public Sector Accounting Standard (IPSAS) for the public entities in Nigeria. Ngama (2012) opines that the implementation of IPSAS in Nigeria would promote a peer – review mechanism of financial reports among the three tiers of government. He further stresses that the adoption of IPSAS will serve as foundation for the preparation of quality financial statements and adequate reporting system in Nigeria Public Sector. Ngama (2012) also reported that the adoption of IPSAS would provide the basis for the establishment of a harmonized budgetary system for the three tiers of government. He added that the era of IPSAS would also enhance the country's eligibility to access economic benefits from donor agencies, private sector, Financial Institutions and Worldwide Financial Institutions such as the World Bank. The preparation of the country's financial statement using IPSAS will definitely encourage investors into the country. Furthermore, it would also expose the in-house corrupt practice of some of the public officers thereby deterring them from such act. Nongo (2014) documented that the adoption of IPSAS in the public sector accounting reporting system will enhance better service delivery in the public sector, support efficient internal control and bring into focus the performances of the agencies. It will also enhance creditability of government financial information and help build confidence of Nigerian citizens and Nigeria development partners both within and abroad. The adoption of IPSAS would also enhance access of information to the public thereby promoting of freedom of information Act 2011 and facilitating the expression of individuals' opinion on government activities. Adoption of IPSAS at the Local Government will also help to fight corruption at the local government level that cause by of lack proper accounting system.

Challenges facing the adoption of IPSAS in Nigeria

Nigeria like developed countries and other developing countries is expected to adopt the international public sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS). Adopting the standard will be good for Nigeria state because it will help to improve her accounting and financial reporting system to international accepted standards (Onwubuariri, 2012). To this effect federal executive council in July 2010 gave full approval for the adoption of IPSAS for the public sector and pronounced that for the all government agencies at all level (federal, state or local government) are expected to adopt IPSAS expected by 2013. The institute of chartered Accountants of Nigeria along with other non-governmental organizations also endorse the Adoption of IPSAS by Nigerian public sector as a basis for financial reporting because of the transparency and accountability element in the reporting system. Nigeria was supposed to adopt the first part of the standard, which is the cash basis in 2013 but this was not possible due to some inherent challenges of IPSAS Adoption. Though adopting the cash basis is not an easy task, no country in the world can boast full adoption of the cash basis because it entails production of consolidated financial statement for all controlled entities, ministries and Parastatals. For this reason many countries started the adoption of IPSAS with the accrual basis first to taste the waters. For Nigeria, the adoption date of the cash basis is was shifted to 2014 and all hands are on desk trying to meet up with the adoption this year. The accrual basis will be adopted in 2016. The sub-committees to work out the modalities for the adoption of IPSAS by the three tiers of Government have been organising workshop, field trips and seminars on IPSAS in all the six – geo political zones of the country to ensure its reality. According to Nango (2014) the subcommittee has gone far in reviewing the current book-keeping system, accounting and reporting system and chat of account currently used by the three tiers of government. The committee started its interactive session with the political leaders, key officers in Federal ministries, permanent secretaries state governors, relevant commissioners within the 36 State and Local Governments. This is to enable the committee to obtain information on all aspects of their budgeting. Book – keeping and financial accounting reporting system. In other to enhance effective adoption and implementation of IPSAS in Nigeria the Sub– Committee of FAAC have developed the following for all government – establishments in Nigeria. Uniform National Chart of Account and User manual for the chat, uniform accounting policies and uniform budget templates that align with IPSAS cash basis format of general purpose financial statements for both cash accrual basis of IPSAS.

However, all efforts put in for adoption of IPSAS in the Nigeria public sectors have yielded no success due to some apparent challenges. It was due to these challenges of course that January 2013 being the target date for IPSAS adoption in Nigeria was a reality and led to the extension of adoption date to January, 2016 for accrual basis IPSAS and 2014 for the cash basis. The Nigeria public sector is also characterized by high level of reluctance in accepting changes especially on financial matters because of the corrupt attitudes some senior officers in this sector. Furthermore, the cost of implementing the standard is enormous and will involve lot money for training personnel, writing of new accounting manuals, installation of adequate information and communication technology software for the program. Federal, State and Local government. Another major challenge- is the fact Nigerian economics system is very porous and it incapable of holding local accounting standard let alone an international standard that will expose all activities to world. Also the constitution need to be amended for it embrace the new standard or the standard needed for the preparation of public sector financial statement (Nkoyo, 2012). In Nigeria, the amendment of our constitution is always a long process and time consuming. At present there is grossly inadequate staff in the various government establishments to handle the implementation of IPSAS (Adebimpe, 2012). John (2011) documents that adoption of IPSAS in Nigeria face so major challenges as follows; First, resistance from officers. It is obvious that not all government administrative machineries such as ministries, parastatals and extra – ministerial departments are supporting IPSAS adoption in Nigeria. Without any doubt, this resistance is due fact that IPSAS will help to unravel all forms of financial malpractices existing in the public sector, hence has become a treat to these stakeholder in the public sectors. Second, the use of common languages to bring across culture and government in the public sector remains a key challenge. Some terminologies used in IPSAS may not be applicable some to countries' financial reporting system due to their uniqueness. This however calls for thorough GAAP analysis.

Third, as part of the effort toward IPSAS adoption, accounting manual need to written to be able to incorporate IPSAS terminologies and other finance officers in the public sector need to be educated and trained on the

application of IPSAS. All these cost good amount of money which may not be readily available or where available but mix-applied by public officers. Finally, insufficient number of qualified accountants in the Nigerian public sector. Most of the state and federal ministries and government agencies lack the necessary accounting personnel to adequately carryout the switch over to IPSAS as opposed to the financial reporting frame work currently in existence

Objective of the study

The broad objective of this is to find study the changelings and the prospects of adoption of IPSAS by government agencies in Nigeria, while the specific objectives are to:

1. ascertain if the implementation of IPSAS will improve the reliability of financial management in Nigeria;
2. find out if adoption of IPSAS will enhance comparability of public sector reports in Nigeria and International best practice;
3. investigate if the availability of finance is a major challenge facing the adoption of IPSAS by the Nigerian public sector; and
4. find out if there is internal resistance from civil servants against the adoption of IPSAS by the Nigerian public sector

METHODOLOGY

Sample size and sampling technique

The research is a descriptive survey research. The design was used for making decision on the data sourced research instrument sampling, plan and content method.

The population of the study comprises all members of staff in accounting department in all state and federal ministries and government agencies in Abuja.

The sample comprises one hundred fifty respondents. These respondents was drawn from some selected Federal government agencies in Federal capital territory. Simple random sampling technique will be used to select the sample this is done to enhance randomization and to eschew biasness of sample chosen

The primary data is the main source the information used in this study. This was via questionnaire.

Method of data analysis

The data will be analyzed using the chi-square technique and z-test. Z- test is used to determine whether two population means are different when the variances are known and sample is large. We will also perform some pre-test like; descriptive statistic and question pretest to enable us to ascertain the validity and reliability of questionnaire.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Figure 1 Professional accountants

Source: Researcher’s computation 2017

From the analysis of the responses retrieved, of the 24 respondents whose responses were used for the analysis, 24(16%) of the respondents are chartered accountants while 126(84%) are not chartered accountants

Figure2

From the analysis of the responses retrieved from 150 respondents whose responses were used for the analysis, 21(14%) of the respondents have work experience of 0-11 while 57(38%) of the respondents are have work experience that fall the range of 11-20 years. Furthermore, 23 (15%) of the respondents have work experience that fall within the range of 21-30 while 49(32%) have above 35years work experience.

Figure3

Source: Researcher’s computation 2017

From the analysis of the responses retrieved, of the 150 respondents whose responses were used for the analysis, 66% of the respondents female while represents 34% of the respondents are male.

Figure 4

Source: Researcher’s computation 2017

From the analysis of the responses retrieved, of the 150 respondents whose responses were used for the analysis, 37(18%) of the respondents can use accounting software while 123(82%) of the respondents cannot use accounting software. Figure also shows that 12(8%) of respondents have attended training within last 12months while 138(92%) of the respondents have not attended any train within last 12 months

Responses from field

The study has 16 statements designed to gather information from field. The responses are analyse as follows:

Statement 1: The adoption of IPSAS will enhance better disclosure of public sector financial accounting. From appendix 2 the analysis of the responses to statement *indicates* that 80 respondents ticked strongly agree, 21 ticked agree while 19 and 30 of them ticked disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively.

Statement 2: Report prepared with IPSAS is subject to more manipulations.

The analysis of the response to statement 2 shows that 9 of the respondents chose strongly agree while 10 of the respondents ticked agree. Also, 91 and 40 of them ticked strongly agreed and agreed option respectively.

Statement 3: The adoption of IPSAS will enhance more credible financial management

The analysis of the response to statement 3 *reveals* that 102 and 28 of the respondents ticked strongly agree and agree respectively while 7 and 13 chose disagree and strongly disagree.

Statement 4: Adoption of IPSAS will better expose fraudulent transactions.

The analysis of the response to statement 4 indicates that of the total of 150 respondents, 88 and 44 ticked strongly agree and agree respectively while 5 and 11 of the respondents chose disagree and strongly disagree options.

Statement 5 Adoption of IPSAS will enhance better comparability financial statements prepared in different countries

The analysis of the responses to statement 5 *indicates* that 109 and 11 ticked strongly agree and agree respectively while 18 and 12 of the total respondents chose disagree and strongly disagree options respectively.

Statement 6: Report using IPSAS permits better comparability of information which assists in the international classification of nations.

The analysis of the response to statement 6 indicates that 75 and 41 of the total retrieved questionnaires ticked the strongly agree and agree options respectively while 24 and 20 chose the disagree and strongly disagree option.

Statement: 7 Adoption of IPSAS will better enhance comparability of the performance of various States governments in Nigeria

The survey of the responses to statement 7 *indicates* that, 105 and 21 respondents of the total retrieved questionnaires ticked the strongly agree and agree options respectively while 14 and 6 ticked disagree and strongly disagree options.

Statement 8 : Civil service has enough money to fund the logistics involve in the switching over process.

The responses survey to statement 8 *indicates* that 5 and 8 of the total retrieved questionnaires ticked the strongly agree and agree options respectively while 47 and 90 of the respondents ticked disagree and strongly disagree options.

Statement 9 : Federal and state ministries, agencies have enough IPSAS trained accountants to power the switch over to IPSAS

The responses survey to statement 9 indicates that 9 and 11 of the respondents ticked strongly agree and agree options respectively while 100 and 30 of them ticked disagree and strongly disagree respectively.

Statement 10: State and Federal ministries have enough computer and software to switch over to IPSAS. The response to statement10 *shows* that 2 and 18 of the respondents ticked strongly agree and agree options while 90 and 40 of the respondents ticked disagree and strongly disagree.

Statement 11: Federal and state ministries, agencies professional accountants power the switch over to IPSAS .The responses to statement 11 indicates that 4 and 16 of the respondents ticked strongly disagree and agree options respectively while 101 and 29 ticked disagree and strongly disagree respectively.

Statement 12: Civil Servants will resist adoption of IPSAS because it will expose corrupt practices in the public sector.The response to statement12 shows that 102 respondents ticked strongly agree, while 38 of the respondents chose agree. Also, 2 and 8 of the respondents ticked disagree and strongly disagree option.

Question 13:The genuineness of report prepared using IPSAS cannot be questioned

The analysis of the response to statement 3 reveals that 121 and 38 of the respondents ticked strongly agree and agree respectively while 1 and 9 chose disagree and strongly disagree.

Question 14: Civil servant are reluctant to switch to IPSAS

The analysis of the response to statement 14 indicates that of the total of 150 respondents, 133 and 8 of them ticked strongly agree and agree respectively while 1 and 6 of the respondents chose the disagree and strongly disagree options.

Statement 15: Top public officers are working against the adoption of IPSAS

The analysis of the responses to statement 5 indicates that 90 and 17 ticked strongly agree and agree respectively while 23 and 30 of the total respondents chose disagree and strongly disagree options respectively.

Statement 16: Report using IPSAS permits better comparability of information which assists in the international classification of nations

The analysis of the response to statement 16 indicates that 121 and 19 of the total retrieved questionnaires ticked the strongly agree and agree option respectively while 2 and 8 chose the disagree and strongly disagree option.

Findings of the study

- i. Implementation of IPSAS not will improve the reliability of financial management in Nigeria.

Table 1 z-Test: Two Sample for Means

	IPSAS	PSA
Mean	27.5	17
Known Variance	7	8
Observations	2	2
Hypothesized Mean Difference	25	
Z	-5.29465	
P(Z<=z) one-tail	0.03196	
z Critical one-tail	1.644854	
P(Z<=z) two-tail	0.0107	
z Critical two-tail	1.959964	

Source: Researcher's computation

The paired sample Z-test for one tail test shows a p-values of 0.031 for one tail test, while p-value for two tail test stood at a value of 0.001. The critical for one tail and two tail test stood at 1.6 and 1.95 respectively. We therefore conclude that the null hypothesis could not be retained for both one and two tail test at 0.25 and 0.05 level of significant respectively in line with the thumb rule ($0.03 < 0.025, 0.01 < 0.05$). The result further shows that z-value is -5.2. This implies switch to IPSAS will increase the reliable of financial management in the Nigerian public sector.

.Test of hypothesis Two

- ii. Adoption of IPSAS will not enhance comparability of public sector reports in Nigeria and International best practice.

Table 2 z-Test: Two Sample for Means

	<i>FA</i>	<i>EEF</i>
Mean	27	16.5
Known Variance	7	8
Observations	2	2
Hypothesized Mean Difference	1	
Z	1.46891	
P(Z<=z) one-tail	0.000261	
z Critical one-tail	1.644854	
P(Z<=z) two-tail	0.000523	
z Critical two-tail	1.959964	

Source: Researcher' computation

The paired sample Z-test for one tail test shows a p-values of 0.002 for one tail test, while p-value for two tail test stood at a value of 0.0005. The critical for one tail and two tail test stood at 1.6 and 1.9 respectively. We therefore conclude that the null hypothesis would not be for both one and two tail test at 0.25 and 0.05 level of significant respectively in line with the thumb rule ($0.0002 < 0.0005 < 0.05$). Further the critical values exceed z-calculated. This implies that is adoption of IPSAS will enhance better comparability of local and international reports of governments. .

Test for hypothesis three

Availability of finance is not a major challenge facing the adoption of IPSAS by the Nigerian public sector

Table 3 Chi-square Test Statistics

	Statement 9	Statement 10
Chi-Square	28.403 ^a	26.105 ^a
Df	4	4
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000

. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 28.6.

Source: SPSS Output (2016)

Table 3 presents the results for the chi-square test statistics. As observed, all the statements are all significant at 5% level as the asymptotic value of 0.00. Specifically, statement 1 has a chi-square and asymptotic value of 28.403 and .00 respectively. Statement 3 has a chi-square and asymptotic value of 26.105 and 0.00 respectively. All the asymptotic values are less than the alpha value of 0.05 at 5% significance level and the calculated chi-square also exceeds the theoretical value at 5%. In the light of the above, we reject the null hypothesis that availability of finance is not a major challenge facing the adoption of IPSAS by the Nigerian public sector.

Hypothesis four

H₀ There is no internal resistance from civil servants against the adoption of IPSAS by the Nigerian public sector

Table 4 Chi-square Test Statistics

	Statement 2	Statement 10
Chi-Square	24.629 ^a	16.888 ^a
Df	4	4
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000

Table 4 presents the results for the chi-square test statistics. As observed, all the statements are all significant at 5% level as the asymptotic value of 0.00. Specifically, statement 2 has a chi-square and asymptotic value of 24.629 and .00 respectively. Statement 10 has a chi-square and asymptotic value of 16.888 and 0.00 respectively. All the asymptotic values are less than the alpha value of 0.05 at 5% significance level and the calculated chi-square also exceeds the theoretical value at 5% .In the light of the above, we reject the null hypothesis which states there is no internal resistance from civil servants against the adoption of IPSAS by the Nigerian public sector

There is no internal resistance from civil servants against the adoption of IPSAS by the Nigerian public sector

Scope/limitation of the study

The topical scope of the study is the perceived impact of IPSAS on government financial management. The geographical scope of the study is forty -five government ministries and agencies in Benin City. The major limitations of this study is the scope and slow responses from respondents.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The rate of fraud in the Nigerian public is astronomical over the years. Most ministries at both state and federal have not prepare financial statement neither have been audited. Nigerian civil servants leverage on the loopholes that associated with the GAAP method report presentation. This study however is aimed at ascertaining the prospects and challenges of adoptions of IPSAS by the Nigerian public sector. The results shows that adoption of IPSAS will reliability of reports prepared by Nigerian public sector. The result also shows that adoption of IPSAS will enhance better comparability of financial report among various state government and between Nigerian and other countries. This go A long way to give Nigeria stand to access fund from international donors Furthermore, the study shows that available fund is a major impediment of the adoption of IPSAS by the Nigerian public sector. The reveal that fund have not been available for training of civil servants on IPSAS software. The also reveals that very few of accountants are qualified chartered accountants and fund has needed for employment of more qualified accountant has been made available to the various ministries.

Finally, the result shows that there internal resist from top government functionaries against the adoption of IPSAS because they are afraid that it expose their fraud because IPSAS is principle based or unlike the rule based that is in presently in place.

The study recommended that the federal government should release fund to power the adoption IPSAS. Accountants in public should be trained on new accounting software that enhance their understandability of IPSAS. Government should display the political for adoption by mandating all ministries and government agencies to switch over to IPSAS and defaulters should be duly sanctioned

REFERENCES

- Achua, J. K. (2009). Reinventing Governmental Account-ing for Accountability Assurance in Nigeria. *Nigeria Research Journal of Accountancy*, 1(1), 1-16.
- Adams R.A, (2010). *Public Sector Accounting and Finance*; Lagos: Corporate Publishers Ventures.
- Adegite, E. O. (2010). Accounting, Accountability and National Development. *Nigerian Accountant*, 43(1), 56-64.

Appah, E. and Appiah, K. Z. A. (2010). Fraud and Development of Sound Financial Institutions in Nigeria. Nigerian Journal for Development Research, 1(1), 49-56.

Aquino, A. C. B. de, Cardoso, R. L. (2012). *Accounting maturity in Brazilian public sector*. In: EIASM (European Institute for Advanced Studies in Management), 7th International Conference on Accounting,

Auditing & Management in Public Sector Reforms. Italy, Milan 04-06 September 2012.

Arnaboldi, M., Lapsley, I. (2009). On the implementation of accrual accounting: *a study of conflict and ambiguity*. *European Accounting Review*, 18(4), 809-836.

Ball, I., Pflugrath, G. (2012) *Government Accounting: Making Enron look good*. World Economics Journal. 13 (1), 1-18.

Barton, A. (2005). *Professional Accounting Standards and the Public Sector - a Mismatch*. Abacus, 41 (2), 138-158.

Bello, S. (2001). Fraud Prevention and Control in Nigerian Public Service: The need for a Dimensional Approach. Journal of Business Administration, 1(2), 118-133

Benito, B., Brusca, I., & Montesinos, V. (2007). *The Harmonization of Government Financial Information Systems: The Role of the IPSASs*, International Review of Administrative Sciences, 73 (2), pp. 293-317.

Berger, T. M. M. (2012). *IPSAS Explained: A Summary of International Public Sector Accounting Standards*. Wiley.

Bunea-Bontas, C.A., & Petre, M.C. (2009). *Arguments for introducing accrual based accounting in the public sector*. **Social Science Research Network (SSRN)**. Available from: <http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1491663>. [Accessed 6th Nov, 2012].

Carnegie, G., & West, B. P. (2003). *How well does accrual accounting fit the public sector?* Australian Journal of Public Administration, 62 (2), 83-86

Carvalho, J., Jorge, S., & Fernandes, M. J. (2006) *New local government accounting in Portugal*. Public Money & Management, 26(4), 211-216.

Chan J. (2008). International Public Sector Accounting Standards Conceptual and Institutional Issues.

Chan, I. J. (2008). International Public Sector Accounting Standards: Conceptual and Institutional Issues. Retrieved July 2, 2010 from <http://jameslchan.com/papers/ChanCagSem5.pdf>.

Chan, J. L. (2003). *Government Accounting: An Assessment of Theory, Purposes and Standards*,

Christensen, M. (2005), *The 'third hand': Private sector consultants in public sector accounting changes*, European Accounting Review, 14(3), pp. 447-474.

Christiaens, J., Reyniers, B., Rollé, C. (2010). *Impact of IPSAS on reforming governmental financial information systems: a comparative study*. **International Review of Administrative**

Egwuonwu, P. (2007). *Financial Reporting: the theoretical and Regulatory Framework* (2nd ed.) Lagos : Oladimeji publishers LTD.

Grossi, G., Sorvechia, M., (2011). *European Commission Adoption of IPSAS to Reform Financial Reporting*. ABACUS, 47 (4), 525-552.

Guthrie, J., Olson, O., & Humphrey, C. (1999). *Debating developments in new public financial management: the limits of global theorising and some new ways forward*. *Financial Accountability & Management*, 15(3-4), pp. 209-228.

Hayfron, A. (2012), *IPSAS and Its Objectives*. IPSAS Hardwork Published March, 2011.

Hood, C. (1991). *A Public Management for All Seasons*. *Public Administration*, 69 (1), 3-19

Hyndman, N., Connolly, C., (2011). *Accruals accounting in the public sector: a road not always taken*. *Management Accounting Research*, 22(1), 36-45.

Izedonmi, F., Ibadin, P. O. (2013). *International Public Sector Accounting Framework, Regulatory Agencies and Standard Setting Procedures: A Critique*. Retrieved from www.iiste.org. ISSN 2222-1905 (Paper) ISSN 2222-2839 (Online).

Jackson, A., Lapsley, I. (2003). The diffusion of accounting practices in the new "managerial" public sector. *The International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 16(5), 359- 372.

Johnson, I. E. (2004). *Public Sector Accounting and Financial Control*. Lagos: Financial Institutions Training Centre.

Jones, R. (2004). *Reforming governmental accounting and budgeting in Europe*. Fachverlag Moderne Wirtschaft, 941-1013

Kaufman, D. (2005). *Myths and Realities of Governance and Corruption*. World Bank Governance Programme, Washington, DC.

Keefer, P. & Khemani, S. (2004). «Democracy, Public Expenditure and the Poor», World Bank Research Observer. World Bank, Washington, D.C.

Khan, A., & Mayes, S. (2009) *Transition to Accrual Accounting*, Technical Note, International Monetary Fund, Fiscal Affairs Department.

John C. (2011), *IPSAS Adoption in Nigeria Step to Improved Accountability in the Nigeria Public Sector*

Lapsley, I., Mussari, R., & Paulsson, G. (2009). *On the Adoption of Accrual Accounting in the Public Sector: A Self-Evident and Problematic Reform*. *European Accounting Review*, 18 (4), 719-723.

Premchand, A. (1999). *Public Financial Accountability in Schviavo-Campo*, S. (ed). *Governance, Corruption and Public Financial Management*. Asian Development Bank. Manila, Philippines. www.adb.org

Onuorah, A. C. & Appah, E. (2012). *Accountability and Public Sector Financial Management in Nigeria*. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (OMAN Chapter)*, 1(6): 1-17.

Olamide, F. (2010). *Audit Quality, Corporate Governance and Firm characteristics in Nigeria*. *International Journal of Business Management* December, 5(5): 10-15

Ojiakor, N. (2009). *Nigerian Socio-political Development: Issues and Problems*. Enugu: John Jacobs Classic Publishers.

Okoye, E. I. & Ani, W. U. (2004). *Analys of Government and Public Sector Accounting*. Imo: Rex Charles and Patrick Limited.

Omolehinwa, E. O., & Naiyeju, J. K. (2011). *Theory and Practice of Government Accounting in Nigeria*. Lagos: Pumarck Nigeria Ltd.

Nongo J. Y. (2014). *IPSAS Issue for Public Finance Management Executive – IPSAS Outlook*. E.Y com/IPSAS.

Oulasvirta L. (2012). The Reluctance of a Development Country to Choose

Ngama, Y. (2012). Nigeria on Tract on IPSAS Implementation Workshop Abuja, International Public Sector Accounting Standards of IFAAC A Critical Case Study, University of Tampere School of Finland

Nweze, A. U. (2013), Using IPSAS to drive Public Sector Accounting. An article published in 2013 ICAN Journal.

Tanzi, V. (1999). “Governance, Corruption, and Public Finance: An Overview”, in Schviano-Campo, S. (ed). “Go-vernance, Corruption and Public Financial Management”, Asian Development Bank, Manila, Philippines. www.adb.org

Ter- Bogt, H. J., & Van -Helden, G. J. (2000), *Accounting Change in Dutch Government: Exploring the Gap Between Expectations and Realizations*, *Management Accounting Research*, 11(2), pp. 263-279.

Wynne, A. (2004), *Do private sector financial statements provide a suitable model for public sector accounts?*, Paper Presented at the European Group of Public Administration Annual Conference on Public Law and the Modernising State, Oeiras (Portugal), 3-6 Sep. 2003.

QUESTIONIARE

Section A

Instruction: Tick as Appropriate

1. What group of employee do you belong to? Chartered- accountant [] ;
Non- chartered Accountant []
2. For how long have you been holding the position? Below 0-10 [] 11-20 [] 21-30;
Above 35 []
3. Sex? Male [], Female []
4. How training have attended in last twelve months: 1 [], 2 [], 3 [], above 4 [], none []
5. Can you use any accounting software: No [] Yes []

Section B

		SA	A	UD	D	SD
	Creditability of financial management					
1.	Through the adoption of IPSAS will enhance full disclosure of public sector financial accounting					
2.	Report prepared with IPSAS is subject to more manipulated					
3.	Will adoption of IPSAS will enhance credible financial management					
4.	Adoption of IPSAS will expose fraudulent transactions					
	Comparability of financial management					
5.	Adoption of IPSAS enhances the comparability financial statements prepared in different countries					
6.	Report using IPSAS permits comparability of information which assists in the international classification of nations					
7.	IPSAS enhance comparability of the performance of various States government in					

	Nigeria					
	Availability of Human capital and resources					
8	Civil service does not enough fund to switch over.					
9	Federal and state ministries, agencies do not trained accountants to power the switch over to IPSAS					
10	State and Federal ministries do not enough computer and software to switch over to IPSAS					
11	State and federal ministries and government agencies have the necessary accounting personnel					
	Internal resistance					
12	Civil Servants will resist adoption because it will expose corrupt practices in the public sector					
13	Report genuineness of report prepared using IPSAS cannot be questioned					
14	Civil servant are not reluctant to switch to IPSAS					
15	Top public officers are not working against the adoption of IPSAS					
16	Civil servants are afraid that adoption of IPSAS will expose any transaction fail to follow due process					

Responses from respondents Table 1

	SA	A	UD	D	SD	TOTAL
1.	80	21	0	19	30	150
2	91	40	0	9	10	150
3.	102	28	0	7	13	150
4	80	44	0	5	21	150
5	109	11	0	18	12	150
6	75	41	0	24	20	150
7	109	21	0	14	6	150
8	4	9	0	47	90	150
9	1	11	0	100	30	150
10	2	18	0	90	40	150
11	4	16	0	101	29	150
12	102	38	0	2	8	150
13	121	19	0	1	9	150
14	133	8	0	1	6	150
15	90	17	0	23	30	150
16	121	19	0	2	8	28